

Carbon Nanotube/Polycaprolactone Composite Filaments Used for 3D Printing

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Outline

- Background
- Results and discussion
- Conclusions

Materials

PCL

Polycaprolactone

Melting point: 60°C

MWCNT

Multiwall carbon nanotube

Surfactant: SDS
sodium dodecyl sulfate

Surfactant: SDBS
sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate

Thermal Stability

All materials are stable up to 180°C.

Filament Synthesis

Filaments

SDS-modified CNT

SDBS-modified CNT

Filament diameter: ~2.6 mm
Filament length: > 1 m

Microstructure

Filament with 40% CNT loading
Non-modified CNT

Filament with 50% CNT loading
SDS-modified CNT

The distribution of CNTs is more uniform with SDS treatment.

Effects of Surfactant

- The optimal ratio of SDS to CNT is 1:30.
- The optimal ratio of SDBS to CNT is 1:15.

Electrical Conductivity

- The σ of the filaments with non-modified CNTs is 10-50 S/m.
- The maximum σ of the filaments with SDBS-modified CNTs is ~300 S/m.
- The maximum σ of the filaments with SDS-modified CNTs is ~400 S/m.

3D Printing

Filament goes in here

Printing temperature: 165°C

PCL with 2% CNT

Pure PCL

Conclusions

- CNT/PCL composite filaments are synthesized by extruding.
- The largest electrical conductivity of the composite filament is ~ 400 S/m.
- A filament with a CNT loading of 2% can be used for 3D printing.

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Thank you for your attention!